

Framtidens arbetsmiljö – trender, digitalisering och anställningsformer

Bilagor
Exkluderade studier

FRAMTIDENS ARBETSMILJÖ – TRENDER,
DIGITALISERING OCH ANSTÄLLNINGSFORMER

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Del 1 – Arbetsmiljötrender

Bilaga
Exkluderade studier

Jörgen Eklund

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Del 2 – Digitalisering och arbetsmiljö

Bilaga
Exkluderade studier

Kristina Palm
Ann Bergman
Calle Rosengren

Relevansbedömning av fulltexter

Tabell över studier som vid fulltextgranskning inte bedöms vara relevanta för forskningsfrågan, PICO/PEO och inklusion- och exklusionskriterierna.

Referens	Motivering för exklusion - ange det mest väsentliga skälet ("Fasta/förutbestämda orsaker": fel outcome (O) , fel population (P), fel exponering/intervention (P)etc.)
Jung, J., Nitzsche, A., Neumann, M., Wirtz, M., Kowalski, C., Wasem, J., ... Pfaff, H. (2010). The Worksite Health Promotion Capacity Instrument (WHPCI): Development, validation and approaches for determining companies' levels of health promotion capacity. <i>BMC Public Health</i> , 10. https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2458-10-550	fel E; fel O; fel P
Thatcher, S. M. B., & Bagger, J. (2011). Working in Pajamas: Telecommuting, Unfairness Sources, and Unfairness Perceptions. <i>Negotiation and Conflict Management Research</i> , 4(3), 248–276.	Försteförfattare ej från Europa
Halford, S., Lotherington, A. T., Obstfelder, A., & Kukarenko, N. (2015). Technical Change and the Un/Troubling of Gendered Ageing in Healthcare Work. <i>Gender, Work and Organization</i> , 22(5), 495–509.	fel O; fel P
Peters, P., & Batenburg, R. (2015). Telework adoption and formalisation in organizations from a knowledge transfer perspective. <i>International Journal of Work Innovation</i> , 1(3), 251–270.	fel E; fel O
Blackwell, E., Nesbit, M., & Petridis, H. (2017). Survey on the use of CAD-CAM technology by UK and Irish dental technicians. <i>British Dental Journal</i> , 222(9), 689–693.	fel E; fel O; fel P
Peristeras, V., Martínez-Carreras, M. A., Gómez-Skarmeta, A. F., Prinz, W., & Nasirifard, P. (2010). Towards a reference architecture for collaborative work environments. <i>International Journal of E-Collaboration</i> , 6(1), 14–32.	fel E; fel O; fel P
Kwaśniewski, J. (2011). The use of monitoring to improve the reliability and endurance of continuous coal handling systems. <i>Archives of Mining Sciences</i> , 56(4), 651–664.	fel E; fel O; fel P
Šekoranja, B., Jerbic, B., & Šuligoj, F. (2015). Virtual surface for human-robot interaction. <i>Transactions of Famena</i> , 39(1), 53–64.	fel O; fel P
Goos, M. (2018). The impact of technological progress on labour markets: Policy challenges. <i>Oxford Review of Economic Policy</i> , 34(3), 362–375.	fel E; fel O; fel P
Skjølvik, T., & Breunig, K. J. (2018). Virtual law firms: An exploration of the media coverage of an emerging archetype. <i>International Journal of Law and Information Technology</i> , 26(1), 64–88.	fel O; fel P;
Carlotto, M. S., Wendt, G. W., & Jones, A. P. (2017). Tecno-estrés, compromiso con la carrera, satisfacción con la vida y la interacción trabajo-familia en trabajadores de la información y tecnologías de la comunicación. <i>Actualidades En Psicología</i> , 31(122), 91.	Försteförfattare ej från Europa

Referens	Motivering för exklusion - ange det mest väsentliga skälet ("Fasta/förutbestämda orsaker": fel outcome (O) , fel population (P), fel exponering/intervention (P)etc.)
Yang, X., & Kah, P. (2015). The analysis of the relationship among the different factors influencing welding production by the gephi software. <i>International Review of Mechanical Engineering</i> , 9(5), 491–498.	fel O; fel P
Rincon, J. A., Costa, A., Novais, P., Julian, V., & Carrascosa, C. (2017). Using emotions in intelligent virtual environments: The EJaCallIVE framework. <i>Wireless Communications and Mobile Computing</i> , 2017.	fel O; fel P
Keijer, U., & Breding, J. (2012). Work life, new technology and employment of disabled people: A twenty year programme. <i>Technology and Disability</i> , 24(3), 211–218.	fel O; fel P
Hynes, M. (2012). ThHynes, M. (2012). The practices of technology: Putting society and technology in their rightful place. <i>International Journal of Technology, Knowledge and Society</i> , 8(3), 27–44.	fel O; fel P
Pianta, M. (2018). Technology and Employment: Twelve Stylised Facts for the Digital Age. <i>Indian Journal of Labour Economics</i> , 61(2), 189–225.	fel O; fel P
Bröchner, J., Haugen, T. & Lindkvist, C. (2018) Shaping tomorrow's facilities management. <i>Facilities</i> , 37(7), 366-380	fel P
Koulouri, T., Lauria, S., & Macredie, R. D. (2017). The influence of visual feedback and gender dynamics on performance, perception and communication strategies in CSCW. <i>International Journal of Human Computer Studies</i> , 97, 162–181.	fel P
Martin, L. (2011). The effects of ICT use on employee's motivations: An empirical evaluation. <i>Economics Bulletin</i> , 31(2), 1592–1605.	fel O; fel P
Archer-Brown, C., Marder, B., Calvard, T., & Kowalski, T. (2018). Hybrid social media: employees' use of a boundary-spanning technology. <i>New Technology, Work and Employment</i> , 33(1), 74–93.	fel O
Vallo Hult, H., Hansson, A., Svensson, L., & Gellerstedt, M. (2019). Flipped healthcare for better or worse. <i>Health Informatics Journal</i> , 25(3), 587–597.	fel O;
Hustad, E. (2017). Knowledge Management in Distributed Work: Implications for Boundary Spanning and its Design. <i>Journal of Integrated Design and Process Science</i> , 21(1), 25–41.	fel O
Askenazy, P., & Caroli, E. (2010). Innovative work practices, information technologies, and working conditions: Evidence for France. <i>Industrial Relations</i> , 49(4), 544–565.	fel P
Gisbert, J. R., Palau, C., Uriarte, M., Prieto, G., Palazón, J. A., Esteve, M., ... González, A. (2014). Integrated system for control and monitoring industrial wireless networks for labor risk prevention. <i>Journal of Network and Computer Applications</i> , 39(1), 233–252.	fel O

Referens	Motivering för exklusion - ange det mest väsentliga skälet ("Fasta/förutbestämda orsaker": fel outcome (O) , fel population (P), fel exponering/intervention (P)etc.)
Pomares, J., Candelas, F. A., Torres, F., Corrales, J. A., & Garc??a, G. J. (2010). Safe human-robot cooperation based on an adaptive time-independent image path tracker. <i>International Journal of Innovative Computing, Information and Control</i> , 6(9), 3819–3842.	fel O
Pfeiffer, M., Kenngott, H., Preukschas, A., Huber, M., Bettscheider, L., Müller-Stich, B., & Speidel, S. (2018). IMHOTEP: virtual reality framework for surgical applications. <i>International Journal of Computer Assisted Radiology and Surgery</i> , 13(5), 741–748.	fel O; fel P
Peters, P., & Heusinkveld, S. (2010). Institutional explanations for managers' attitudes towards telehomeworking. <i>Human Relations</i> , 63(1), 107–135.	fel P
Stock, T., Obenaus, M., Kunz, S., & Kohl, H. (2018). Industry 4.0 as enabler for a sustainable development: A qualitative assessment of its ecological and social potential. <i>Process Safety and Environmental Protection</i> , 118, 254–267.	fel O; fel P
Weiss, A., Igelsböck, J., Wurhofer, D., & Tscheligi, M. (2011). Looking forward to a "robotic society"?: Notions of future human-robot relationships. <i>International Journal of Social Robotics</i> , 3(2), 111–123.	fel O; fel P
Duval, T., Nguyen, T. T. H., Fleury, C., Chauffaut, A., Dumont, G., & Gouranton, V. (2014). Improving awareness for 3D virtual collaboration by embedding the features of users' physical environments and by augmenting interaction tools with cognitive feedback cues. <i>Journal on Multimodal User Interfaces</i> , 8(2), 187–197.	fel O
Leroy, L., Fuchs, P., & Moreau, G. (2012). Real-time adaptive blur for reducing eye strain in stereoscopic displays. <i>ACM Transactions on Applied Perception</i> , 9(2).	fel O
Ceriani, N. M., Zanchettin, A. M., Rocco, P., Stolt, A., & Robertsson, A. (2015). Reactive Task Adaptation Based on Hierarchical Constraints Classification for Safe Industrial Robots. <i>IEEE/ASME Transactions on Mechatronics</i> , 20(6), 2935–2949.	fel O
Lavié, A. H., & Fernandez, A. I. L. (2018). New social intervention technologies as a challenge in social work: IFSW Europe perspective. <i>European Journal of Social Work</i> , 21(6), 824–835.	fel O; fel P
Müller, R., Vette, M., & Scholer, M. (2014). Inspector robot - A new collaborative testing system designed for the automotive final assembly line. <i>Assembly Automation</i> , 34(4), 370–378.	fel O
Ekberg, K., Pransky, G., Besen, E., Fassier, J. B., Feuerstein, M., Munir, F., ... Young, A. E. (2016). New Business Structures Creating Organizational Opportunities and Challenges for Work Disability Prevention. <i>Journal of Occupational Rehabilitation</i> , 26(4), 480–489.	fel O

Referens	Motivering för exklusion - ange det mest väsentliga skälet ("Fasta/förutbestämda orsaker": fel outcome (O) , fel population (P), fel exponering/intervention (P)etc.)
Blok, M. M., Groenesteijn, L., Schelvis, R., & Vink, P. (2012). New ways of working: Does flexibility in time and location of work change work behavior and affect business outcomes? In <i>Work</i> (Vol. 41, pp. 2605–2610).	fel O; fel P
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Ekinsmyth (2014) Mothers' business, work/life and the politics of 'mumpreneurship'. <i>Gender, Place & Culture</i> , 21(10), 1230-1248	fel O;
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Del 3 – Anställningsform, hälsa, arbetstillfredsställelse, arbetsskador och mortalitet – en översikt av översikter

Bilaga
Exkluderade studier

Gunnar Aronsson

Följande 22 vetenskapliga artiklar exkluderades på grund av bristande relevans

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